

Ecological insights from environmental disturbances in mesophotic coral ecosystems

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Citation: Pinheiro, H. T., G. Eyal, B. Shepherd, and L. A. Rocha. 2019. Ecological insights from environmental disturbances in mesophotic coral ecosystems. *Ecosphere* 10(4):e02666. 10.1002/ecs2.2666

Abstract. Mesophotic coral ecosystems (MCEs) have historically been considered more stable than shallow reefs and thus suggested to provide refuge to coral reef communities against natural and anthropogenic impacts. Despite this assumption, a growing body of literature has shown that deep reefs are not immune to natural disturbance. Here, based on our in situ observations, we propose that disturbance may actually represent an important mechanism for maintaining biodiversity in MCEs, as is the case for shallow reefs. Our observations suggest that disturbances can provide microhabitat and space necessary for the recruitment and occurrence of different species, increasing overall diversity. Since bioerosion rates are lower at depth, and most well-developed coral reefs on MCEs are formed by dense aggregations of a single or a few species, intermediate levels of disturbance could represent a critical driver of community structure balancing. Therefore, instead of long-term stability, intermediate disturbances should be expected on MCEs. However, high frequency and intensity of natural disturbances, or their association with anthropogenic stressors, might have stronger negative impacts on MCEs than on shallower reefs due to slower coral growth and calcification rates.

Key words: biodiversity; deep reefs; ecology; natural history; refuge; stability; technical diving.

Received 19 February 2019; accepted 25 February 2019. Corresponding Editor: Debra P. C. Peters.

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Mesophotic coral ecosystems (MCEs) represent the deeper portions of coral reefs and a transition zone between photic and aphotic realms, found between 30 and 150 m depth (Weiss 2017, Rocha et al. 2018). In recent years, improvements in technical diving have allowed researchers to explore and study MCEs more than ever before and have resulted in the discovery of several previously unknown species and descriptions of unique habitats and communities (Pyle 2000, Pinheiro et al. 2014, 2016, Anderson et al. 2016, Rocha et al. 2018). Historically, MCEs have been considered more stable than shallow reefs (Lessaer et al. 2009, Bridge et al. 2011, Slattery et al.

2011, Reardon 2018), and depth has been suggested to provide refuge to coral reef communities against natural and anthropogenic impacts, due to attenuation of wave energy (Kahng et al. 2010), and reduced temperature and ambient light (Glynn 1996, Bridge et al. 2013), leading to the concept known as the “Deep Reef Refuge Hypothesis” (Bongaerts et al. 2010).

However, current observations suggest that deep reefs are not immune to disturbance. In a recent expedition to the Bahamas, diving with closed-circuit rebreathers down to 135 m depth, we observed impacts of Hurricane Matthew and bleaching events from shallow to lower

Fig. 1. Dense aggregation of *Acropora tenella* in the northern Coral Sea (left), and species (indicated by arrows) among mesophotic branching, plate-like, and foliose corals that might benefit from natural disturbances of intermediate levels (right). Sponges (A), other forms of hard corals (B) and soft corals (C) using the free space between and below dead part of plate-like corals. This colonization pattern is also frequent on the naturally dead part of the strictly mesophotic coral *Euphyllia paradivisa* (D) and on dead part of other growth forms as the foliose coral *Turbinaria reniformis* (E) and massive growth corals (F). Photographs from P. Bongaerts (left) and G. Eyal (right).

mesophotic habitats of the coral reef system (Rocha et al. 2018). Mathew passed through the Bahamas on 5 and 6 October 2016 as a category 4 hurricane, with winds ranging from 100 to 195 km/h. Shallow coral reefs were buried and destroyed. Deeper down the reef, the disturbance was similar, and most of the mesophotic coral reef system was covered by sediment and physically damaged down to 135 m depth. At lower MCEs, we observed free sponges, algae, and broken coral dislodged from shallow waters, along with terrigenous debris such as tree branches. Other hurricanes and cyclones have been reported to impact MCEs in the Caribbean (Bongaerts et al. 2010), the Great Barrier Reef (Bongaerts et al. 2013), Okinawa, Japan (White et al. 2013), and French Polynesia (Harmelin-Vivien and Laboute 1986). Occasional disturbance from sediments on MCEs also occurs in Eilat, Red

Sea, following flashflood events due to the flow of terrestrial hyperpycnal sediment plumes down to upper and lower MCEs (Katz et al. 2015).

Lower temperatures found on MCEs seem to control the lower depth limits of coral communities (Bongaerts et al. 2015). However, recent research suggests that the reef zone between 50 and 130 m depth exhibits a large variability in temperature (Smith et al. 2016b, Baldwin et al. 2018, Schramek et al. 2018). In Eilat, our current observations show that ongoing summer temperature variation is causing mass bleaching events in coral species specialized to the mesophotic zone (Eyal et al. 2019). We also recorded bleached corals down to a depth of 120 m in the Bahamas (Rocha et al. 2018) as in the Great Barrier Reef (Frade et al. 2018).

Natural disturbance episodes have critical ecological roles on shallow coral reefs. As natural

Table 1. Species recorded during four rebreather dives on mesophotic coral ecosystems of the Bahamas disturbed by the Hurricane Mathew on October 2016.

Species	Depth (m)	
	Observed	Literature
<i>Acanthurus chirurgus</i> †	30	0–25
<i>Apsilus dentatus</i> †	70	100–300
<i>Balistes vetula</i>	70	2–275
<i>Canthigaster jamestyleri</i> †	70	90–100
<i>Canthigaster rostrata</i>	35	1–40
<i>Caranx latus</i>	35	0–140
<i>Caranx lugubris</i>	60	12–354
<i>Caranx ruber</i> †	70	0–35
<i>Carcharhinus perezii</i>	5–65	1–65
<i>Centropyge argi</i>	15–70	5–80
<i>Cephalopholis cruentata</i>	30–70	0–170
<i>Chaetodon sedentarius</i>	70	5–92
<i>Chromis aff. enchrysur</i>	70–110	5–146
<i>Chromis cyanea</i> †	30–75	3–60
<i>Chromis enchrysur</i>	45	5–146
<i>Chromis insolata</i>	30–100	20–100
<i>Clepticus parrae</i>	50–70	8–100
<i>Coryphopterus hialinus</i>	30–70	8–52
<i>Coryphopterus personatus</i>	30–70	3–46
<i>Coryphopterus sp.</i>	35	
<i>Elacatinus evelynae</i> †	70	1–53
<i>Elacatinus louisae</i> †	70	13–45
<i>Equetus punctatus</i>	30	3–30
Gobiidae sp.	95	
<i>Gramma linki</i>	50–70	27–130
<i>Gramma loreto</i>	30–45	1–60
<i>Gramma melacara</i>	30–70	10–180
<i>Haemulon plumieri</i> †	70	3–40
<i>Halichoeres garnoti</i> †	20–130	2–80
<i>Holacanthus ciliaris</i>	70	1–70
<i>Holacanthus tricolor</i>	65–70	3–92
<i>Holocentrus adscensionis</i>	30	0–180
<i>Holocentrus rufus</i> †	30–70	0–32
<i>Hypoplectrus unicolor</i> †	35	1–20
<i>Kyphosus sp.</i>	30	
<i>Lactophrys bicaudalis</i> †	95	3–50
<i>Liopropoma carmabi</i>	70	15–70
<i>Liopropoma mowbrayi</i> †	30–70	30–60
<i>Liopropoma olneyi</i> †	105–130	123–220
<i>Lipogramma klayi</i> †	35–100	45–145
<i>Lucayablennius zingaro</i>	85	13–106
<i>Lutjanus buccanella</i>	70	20–200
<i>Mycteroperca tigris</i>	35	10–40
<i>Neoniphon marianus</i> †	70–100	1–70
<i>Pomacanthus paru</i>	65–70	3–100
<i>Prognathodes aculeatus</i>	35–60	1–100
<i>Scarus iseri</i> †	30–70	3–25
<i>Scarus vetula</i> †	30	3–25
<i>Schultzia beta</i> †	35–130	15–110
<i>Serranus annularis</i>	35	10–70

(Table 1. Continued.)

Species	Depth (m)	
	Observed	Literature
<i>Serranus luciopercanus</i>	105–130	
<i>Sphyraena barracuda</i>	70	1–100
<i>Stegastes partitus</i>	30–45	0–100
<i>Thalassoma bifasciatum</i> †	30–70	0–40

Notes: The observed depth and the depth range found in the literature (Froese and Pauly 2018) are provided. A dagger (†) indicates depth range extension.

processes and at intermediate levels, these disturbances maintain the nonequilibrium state of shallow coral reef communities, potentially increasing the biodiversity of these ecosystems (Connell 1978). Instead of long-term stability, as hypothesized in the past, here we present growing evidence that MCEs are not stable environments. Therefore, disturbances might represent an important ecological mechanism for maintaining diversity on MCEs similarly to what occurs in shallow coral reefs.

The most well-developed coral reefs recorded at depth are formed by dense aggregations of a single or few species, such as *Acropora tenella* in the northern Coral Sea (Muir et al. 2018; Fig. 1), *Euphyllia paradivisa* in Eilat's north area (Eyal et al. 2016; Fig. 1D), *Alveopora* spp. in Eilat's south area (Eyal-Shaham et al. 2016), *Leptoseris* spp. in Hawai'i (Kahng and Kelley 2007) and in the Red Sea (Fricke and Schuhmacher 1983), and *Agaricia* spp. in the Caribbean (Hoeksema et al. 2017). Mesophotic coral reefs show lower bioerosion (Weinstein et al. 2014, 2016) and mortality (Laverick and Rogers 2018) rates than shallow reefs, and these plate-like, foliose, or tabular corals commonly cover extensive areas on deep reefs (Kahng et al. 2010). In this context, we propose that disturbance of these communities may actually provide the microhabitat and space necessary for highly successful recruitment (Kramer et al. 2019) and occurrence of different species.

In Eilat, Red Sea, for instance, our observations indicate that disturbance might promote the colonization of many other invertebrates (Octocorallia, Tunicata, Porifera, Bryozoa, Mollusca, Polychaeta, etc.) on the bottom sides of living corals, as well as on top of the dead branches of mesophotic corals (Fig. 1A–F). In the Bahamas, we found a higher richness of reef fish species on

disturbed MCEs (52 species; Table 1) than some previously recorded values on healthy Bahamian deep reefs: 23 species reported by Colin (1976) and 24 by Lesser and Slattery (2011). Twenty species had their depth range extended (Table 1), and some of them might benefit from the increased sedimentation and dislodged sponges and corals, which provide new habitat and feeding opportunities. Recent reports of alterations in coral and benthic composition and coverage in regions such as Pulley Ridge, USA (Slattery et al. 2018), and Verde Island Passage, Philippines (Shepherd et al. 2018), show that the MCE community structure undergoes short-term changes. Tropical storms are hypothesized to structure mesophotic communities in the Caribbean (Smith et al. 2016a), and in Okinawa, a typhoon produced equal damage to deep and shallow corals, causing significant changes in the MCE community structure (White et al. 2013). Earlier studies investigating temporal variation in deep reef communities found the highest diversity of species associated with sites with intermediate levels of change and the lowest diversities with very low change (Liddell and Avery 2000).

Thus, as for shallow reefs (Connell 1978), we propose that intermediate levels of disturbance should be expected, and probably also represent an important mechanism for maintaining long-term biodiversity in MCEs. However, when weakened by stressors such as overfishing, sedimentation, pollution, or invasive species, MCEs may become less resilient to disturbance, as is also the case for shallow coral reefs (Hughes et al. 2007). Since MCE coral species appear to have slow growth and/or calcification rates due to decreased metabolic rates (Kahng et al. 2010, Kahng 2013, Weinstein et al. 2016, Groves et al. 2018), a high frequency and intensity of natural disturbances and their association with anthropogenic stressors could undermine the resilience of the system and cause phase shift scenarios in degraded assemblages.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was funded through the generous support of donors who endorsed the California Academy of Sciences' Hope for Reefs Initiative. GE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie

Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 796025. We are grateful to the two anonymous reviewers and Pim Bongaerts for their constructive comments on the earlier version of the manuscript. We thank the support from Mauritius V. Bell, the Umbra and the Alucia crew, and the Interuniversity Institute for Marine Sciences of Eilat (IUI). We also thank the organizers and participants of the Gordon Research Conference on mesophotic coral ecosystems, held in Lewiston in June 2018, for the opportunity of network and the interesting discussions and conversations.

LITERATURE CITED

- Anderson, W. D., B. D. Greene, and L. A. Rocha. 2016. *Grammatonotus brianne*, a new callanthiid fish from Philippine waters, with short accounts of two other *Grammatonotus* from the Coral Triangle. *Zootaxa* 4173:289–295.
- Baldwin, C. C., L. Tornabene, and D. R. Robertson. 2018. Below the Mesophotic. *Scientific Reports* 8:4920.
- Bongaerts, P., P. R. Frade, K. B. Hay, N. Englebert, K. R. W. Latijnhouwers, R. P. M. Bak, M. J. A. Vermeij, and O. Hoegh-Guldberg. 2015. Deep down on a Caribbean reef: Lower mesophotic depths harbor a specialized coral-endosymbiont community. *Scientific Reports* 5:7652.
- Bongaerts, P., P. Muir, N. Englebert, T. C. L. Bridge, and O. Hoegh-Guldberg. 2013. Cyclone damage at mesophotic depths on Myrmidon Reef (GBR). *Coral Reefs* 32:935.
- Bongaerts, P., T. Ridgway, E. M. Sampayo, and O. Hoegh-Guldberg. 2010. Assessing the 'deep reef refugia' hypothesis: focus on Caribbean reefs. *Coral Reefs* 29:309–327.
- Bridge, T., T. Done, A. Friedman, R. Beaman, S. Williams, O. Pizarro, and J. Webster. 2011. Variability in mesophotic coral reef communities along the Great Barrier Reef, Australia. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 428:63–75.
- Bridge, T. C. L., T. P. Hughes, J. M. Guinotte, and P. Bongaerts. 2013. Call to protect coral reefs. *Nature Climate Change* 3:528–530.
- Colin, P. L. 1976. Observations of deep-reef fishes in the Tongue-of-the-ocean, Bahamas. *Bulletin of Marine Science* 26:603–605.
- Connell, J. H. 1978. Diversity in Tropical Rain Forests and coral reefs. *Science* 199:1302–1310.
- Eyal, G., L. Eyal-Shaham, I. Cohen, O. Ben-Zvi, F. Siniger, and Y. Loya. 2016. *Euphyllia paradivisa*, a successful mesophotic coral in the northern Gulf of Eilat/Aqaba, Red Sea. *Coral Reefs* 35:91–102.
- Eyal, G., R. Tamir, N. Kramer, L. Eyal-Shaham, and Y. Loya. 2019. The Red Sea Mesophotic coral

- ecosystems. Pages 199–214 in Y. Loya, K. A. Puglise, and T. C. L. Bridge, editors. Mesophotic coral ecosystems. Springer, New York, New York, USA.
- Eyal-Shaham, L., G. Eyal, R. Tamir, and Y. Loya. 2016. Reproduction, abundance and survivorship of two *Alveopora* spp. in the mesophotic reefs of Eilat, Red Sea. *Scientific Reports* 6:20964.
- Frade, P. R., P. Bongaerts, N. Englebert, A. Rogers, M. Gonzalez-Rivero, and O. Hoegh-Guldberg. 2018. Deep reefs of the Great Barrier Reef offer limited thermal refuge during mass coral bleaching. *Nature Communications* 9:3447.
- Fricke, H. W., and H. Schuhmacher. 1983. The depth limits of Red Sea stony corals: an ecophysiological problem (a deep diving survey by submersible). *Marine Ecology* 4:163–194.
- Froese, R., and D. Pauly. 2018. Fishbase. www.fishbase.org
- Glynn, P. W. 1996. Coral reef bleaching: facts, hypotheses and implications. *Global Change Biology* 2:495–509.
- Groves, S. H., D. M. Holstein, I. C. Enochs, G. Kolodziej, D. P. Manzello, M. E. Brandt, and T. B. Smith. 2018. Growth rates of *Porites astreoides* and *Orbicella franksi* in mesophotic habitats surrounding St. Thomas, US Virgin Islands. *Coral Reefs* 37:345–354.
- Harmelin-Vivien, M. L., and P. Laboute. 1986. Catastrophic impact of hurricanes on atoll outer reef slopes in the Tuamotu (French Polynesia). *Coral Reefs* 5:55–62.
- Hoeksema, B. W., P. Bongaerts, and C. C. Baldwin. 2017. High coral cover at lower mesophotic depths: a dense *Agaricia* community at the leeward side of Curaçao, Dutch Caribbean. *Marine Biodiversity* 47:67–70.
- Hughes, T. P., M. J. Rodrigues, D. R. Bellwood, D. Caccarelli, O. Hoegh-Guldberg, L. McCook, N. Moltschanivskyj, M. S. Pratchett, R. S. Steneck, and B. Willis. 2007. Phase shifts, herbivory, and the resilience of coral reefs to climate change. *Current Biology* 17:360–365.
- Kahng, S. E. 2013. Growth rate for a zooxanthellate coral (*Leptoseris hawaiiensis*) at 90 m. *Galaxea, Journal of Coral Reef Studies* 15:39–40.
- Kahng, S. E., J. R. Garcia-Sais, H. L. Spalding, E. Brokovich, D. Wagner, E. Weil, L. Hinderstein, and R. J. Toonen. 2010. Community ecology of mesophotic coral reef ecosystems. *Coral Reefs* 29:255–275.
- Kahng, S. E., and C. D. Kelley. 2007. Vertical zonation of megabenthic taxa on a deep photosynthetic reef (50–140 m) in the Au'au Channel, Hawaii. *Coral Reefs* 26:679–687.
- Katz, T., H. Ginat, G. Eyal, Z. Steiner, Y. Braun, S. Shalev, and B. N. Goodman-Tchernov. 2015. Desert flash floods form hyperpycnal flows in the coral-rich Gulf of Aqaba, Red Sea. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 417:87–98.
- Kramer, N., G. Eyal, R. Tamir, and Y. Loya. 2019. Upper mesophotic depths in the coral reefs of Eilat, Red Sea, offer suitable refuge grounds for coral settlement. *Scientific Reports* 9:2263.
- Laverick, J. H., and A. D. Rogers. 2018. Experimental evidence for reduced mortality of *Agaricia lamarcki* on a mesophotic reef. *Marine Environmental Research* 134:37–43.
- Lesser, M. P., and M. Slattery. 2011. Phase shift to algal dominated communities at mesophotic depths associated with lionfish (*Pterois volitans*) invasion on a Bahamian coral reef. *Biological Invasions* 13:1855–1868.
- Lesser, M. P., M. Slattery, and J. J. Leichter. 2009. Ecology of mesophotic coral reefs. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 375:1–8.
- Liddell, W. D., and W. E. Avery. 2000. Temporal change in hard substrate communities 10–250 m, the Bahamas. *Proceedings 9th International Coral Reef Symposium* 2:1–6.
- Muir, P. R., M. Pichon, L. Squire, and C. C. Wallace. 2018. *Acropora tenella*, a zooxanthellate coral extending to 110-m depth in the northern Coral Sea. *Marine Biodiversity*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12526-018-0855-z>
- Pinheiro, H. T., G. Goodbody-Gringley, M. E. Jessup, B. Shepherd, A. D. Chequer, and L. A. Rocha. 2016. Upper and lower mesophotic coral reef fish communities evaluated by underwater visual censuses in two Caribbean locations. *Coral Reefs* 35:139–151.
- Pinheiro, H. T., J.-C. Joyeux, and R. L. Moura. 2014. Reef oases in a seamount chain in the southwestern Atlantic. *Coral Reefs* 33:1113.
- Pyle, R. 2000. Assessing undiscovered fish biodiversity on deep coral reefs using advanced self-contained diving technology. *Marine Technology Society Journal* 34:82–91.
- Reardon, S. 2018. Hurricane Maria's coral-reef clues. *Nature* 560:421–422.
- Rocha, L. A., H. T. Pinheiro, B. Shepherd, Y. P. Papastamatiou, O. J. Luiz, R. L. Pyle, and P. Bongaerts. 2018. Mesophotic coral ecosystems are threatened and ecologically distinct from shallow water reefs. *Science* 361:281–284.
- Schramek, T. A., P. L. Colin, M. A. Merrifield, and E. J. Terrill. 2018. Depth-dependent thermal stress around corals in the tropical Pacific Ocean. *Geophysical Research Letters* 45:9739–9747.
- Shepherd, B., H. T. Pinheiro, and L. A. Rocha. 2018. Ephemeral aggregation of the benthic ctenophore *Lyrocteis imperatoris* on a mesophotic coral

- ecosystem in the Philippines. *Bulletin of Marine Science* 94:101–102.
- Slattery, M., M. P. Lesser, D. Brazeau, M. D. Stokes, and J. J. Leichter. 2011. Connectivity and stability of mesophotic coral reefs. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 408:32–41.
- Slattery, M., S. Moore, L. Boye, S. Whitney, A. Woolsey, and M. Woolsey. 2018. The Pulley Ridge deep reef is not a stable refugia through time. *Coral Reefs* 37:391–396.
- Smith, T. B., V. W. Brandtneris, M. Canals, M. E. Brandt, J. Martens, R. S. Brewer, E. Kadison, M. Kammann, J. Keller, and D. M. Holstein. 2016a. Potential structuring forces on a shelf edge Upper Mesophotic coral ecosystem in the US Virgin Islands. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 3:115.
- Smith, T. B., J. Gyory, M. E. Brandt, W. J. Miller, J. Josart, and R. S. Nemeth. 2016b. Caribbean mesophotic coral ecosystems are unlikely climate change refugia. *Global Change Biology* 22:2756–2765.
- Weinstein, D. K., A. Sharifi, J. S. Klaus, T. B. Smith, S. J. Giri, and K. P. Helmle. 2016. Coral growth, bioerosion, and secondary accretion of living orbicellid corals from mesophotic reefs in the US Virgin Islands. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 559:45–63.
- Weinstein, D. K., T. B. Smith, and J. S. Klaus. 2014. Mesophotic bioerosion: variability and structural impact on U.S. Virgin Island deep reefs. *Geomorphology* 222:14–24.
- Weiss, B. K. R. 2017. Into the twilight zone. *Science* 355:900–904.
- White, K. N., et al. 2013. Typhoon damage on a shallow mesophotic reef in Okinawa, Japan. *PeerJ* 1: e151.